

اسلامی ریاست میں عوام کو نظم و ضبط کا پابند بنانے کے طریقے تعلیمات نبوی ﷺ کی روشنی میں

Ways to Discipline the People in the Islamic State in the light of the teachings of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him)

Maria Khalil

Lecturer, Department of Islamic Studies, Sardar Bahadur Khan Women's University, Quetta.

Dr. Shabana Qazi

Assistant Professor, Department of Islamic Studies, University of Balochistan, Quetta

Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies

01-15

© The Author (s) 2024

Volume:4, Issue:2, 2024

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

OJS **PKP**
OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEMS PUBLIC KNOWLEDGE PROJECT

Abstract

There were great revolutions in the world, some of which had far-reaching effects on human history, but the revolution brought by the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) was in every sense the greatest revolution in human history. Its greatness lies in the fact that the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) not only improved the appearance of the nation, but this revolution changed even within them. Most importantly, this revolution reached its peak in a short span of only twenty-three years and the whole of Arabia was transformed. Thirsting for each other's blood became grateful to each other as if they were a wall of lead. The question is, what was the strategy on the basis of which such a great revolution took place in humanity, and in the short period of thirteen years, such a group of highly trained people was prepared that as soon as a state (in the form of Medina) was found, each member of the pre-trained party handled their assigned task so smoothly as if they were made for it. Human training done with this level of skill can only be the characteristic of a prophet. He carved every person associated with Islam and made him a diamond out of coal. In this regard, an important point in the prophetic strategy adopted by the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) is the establishment of discipline. He disciplined the people not only at the individual level but also at the collective level, which led to the establishment of a true welfare state. This research article first highlights the teachings of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) to organize the masses through worship. This is followed by a light on the Prophet's teachings of maintaining discipline in private and personal life, and finally on the Prophet's principles of maintaining discipline in social life and interpersonal matters.

Keywords: : Prophet Muhammad (SAW), Islamic state, Discipline, Blessings, worship

Corresponding Author Email:

mariakhalil59@gmail.com / shabanaqazi786@yahoo.com